

Data Archiving and Networked Services

Long-Term Preservation Policies for Research Data Repositories: a Template

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Table of Contents

List of Figures	2
List of Tables	2
Part I: Long-Term Preservation Policies for Research Data Repositories	3
1.1 Introduction	3
1.2 Method: Approaches to LTP Policies	4
1.2.1 Some notational conventions	4
1.2.2 LTP Principles	4
1.2.3 Areas to be covered in a LTP Policy	6
1.3 Applying the LTP Policy Template	7
1.3.1 Some considerations when outsourcing LTP	7
1.3.2 The designated community or communities	8
1.3.3 The LTP Policy Template and Curation Levels	9
1.4 Cost modelling for LTP	10
1.4.1 LTP Costs and business models	10
1.4.2 Cost models for LTP	11
Part II: LTP Policy Template	13
Long-Term Preservation Policy Template	13
Contents	13
1. Objectives, scope and delimitation of this policy	13
2. Ingest	14
2A. [LTP Service] is provided by the data service itself	14
2B. [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution]	16
3. Archival Storage	17
4. Data Management	18
5. Administration	20
6. Preservation Planning	21
7. Access	22
Part III: Appendices	24
Appendix 1. Summary of the OAIS Reference Model	25
Mandatory responsibilities	25
The reference model	25
Selected OAIS Definitions (slightly adapted for use in this document)	26
OAIS Functional entities	27
Appendix 2. Recurring monitoring processes for LTP	30

Appendix 3. Legal and Statutory Context and Requirements	32
European legislation and regulations	32
International codes of conduct	32
Data archiving guidelines	33
National legislation and codes of conduct (example for The Netherlands)	33
Appendix 4. Selected terms and abbreviations used	34
List of Abbreviations	35
Part IV: Specifics for EUDAT	37
Appendix 5. Applying the Long-Term Preservation Policy Template	38
EUDAT B2SHARE as a designated community or communities	38
Applying the LTP Policy Template for B2SHARE and B2SAFE	38
Appendix 6. Available Licenses for digital assets uploaded to the EUDAT B2SHARE service	42
Appendix 7. LTP compliance comparison between B2SHARE and B2SAFE	44
Appendix 8. Agreement structure within EUDAT	55

List of Figures

Figure 1. OAIS Functional Entities	26
Figure 2. Current EUDAT agreement structure	51
Figure 3. Data Repository Service is LTP Service	53
Figure 4. Long-term preservation is delegated by Data Repository Service to external LTP Service	53

List of Tables

Table 1. LTP Policy Template sections and curation levels	10
Table 2. Overview of cost models for digital preservation	12
Table 3. Service description of B2SHARE and B2SAFE	37
Table 4. LTP Policy comparison between B2SHARE and B2SAFE	42

Part I: Long-Term Preservation Policies for Research Data Repositories

1.1 Introduction

The aim of this document is to assist research data repositories to formulate a Long-Term Preservation (LTP) policy for the provision of their data services. Although the original work, carried out for the [DICE project](#), was intended especially for developing such policies for the EUDAT services B2SHARE and B2SAFE, the core of the work consists of a “model” LTP Policy, which can serve the long-term preservation needs of a broad range of data repository services¹.

The model LTP Policy takes the form of a “template”, consisting of articles grouped into sections, which can either be used directly by selecting the applicable ones, filling out a variety of options applying to the situation of a repository, or indirectly as a checklist, providing guidance about which policy areas to cover. The template itself is included in Part II of this document ([LTP Policy Template](#)), and is also available as a separate form.

Data service providers can use the model template to create a full LTP Policy document or to include a LTP paragraph in their Service Level Agreements (SLAs) and/or Operational Level Agreements (OLAs). For data services in which LTP plays a minor role, LTP paragraphs can be extracted from the template, in order to clarify to users what is or can be guaranteed, for how long, and by whom.

The LTP Policy Template follows the structure and functional units of ISO standard [14721:2012](#), the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) reference model, from which certification systems such as [CoreTrustSeal](#) are derived (see Appendix 1 for a summary). By adhering to this structure, dedicated archives implementing this LTP Policy Template will be well positioned to certify their service. Most of the [FAIR data principles](#), especially the aspects of Findability, Access and Reusability, are also important in long-term preservation. Therefore, the LTP Policy Template also supports Trustworthy Digital Repositories in the implementation of the FAIR principles.

Because of the modular design of the The LTP Policy Template with numbered sections and articles, from which the applicable ones can be selected, the template can easily be adapted to various situations. Sometimes there are alternative options among which a choice can be made. For instance, the DMP Policy template can be used in cases where long-term preservation is outsourced, as well as in cases where the repository itself takes care of the archiving task. Some considerations connected to this choice are discussed in section 1.3.1 of this report.

¹ The DICE project (Data Infrastructure Capacities for EOSC) has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 project call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020 under Grant Agreement no. 101017207. The LTP Policy Template was designed in such a way that it can be connected to the “EUDAT Service Management Framework”, version 2.5 (19/2/2021).

1.2 Method: Approaches to LTP Policies

For the LTP Policy Template we made ample use of existing work carried out in the development of digital preservation policies. References to websites and online documents providing good practices and other useful materials for digital preservation policies are provided.

1.2.1 Some notational conventions

Throughout this document [square brackets] are used to refer to templated organisations, like [LTP Institution] or a service [LTP Service]. If the LTP Policy Template is used as the basis for an actual policy, these terms are to be replaced by the names of the involved institutions and services.

- [LTP Institution]: the organisation responsible and liable for long-term preservation.
- [LTP Service]: the activities and functions performed to preserve data sets and related assets for the long term.
- (Research) **data repositories** come in many different flavours, but are generally organisations or systems that store (research) data in an organised way for analysis and/or reporting. A research data service is an even broader term, but usually includes a repository function.
- If a data service or repository also runs and operates a [LTP Service], we will refer to it as “**In-house LTP**”. If the [LTP Service] is outsourced to another, dedicated archive, both organisations are required to adopt the LTP Policy, specifying how the various archival functions are distributed over both organisations.
- We sometimes use the term “**dedicated archive**” to indicate a [LTP Institution] that is specialised in providing [LTP Services].
- The term “**research data**” is loosely defined as “**any (digital or analogous) object or evidence that is needed to underpin research**”². The LTP Policy Template deals explicitly with digital data. We use the term here interchangeably with **research datasets** (= data organised in a coherent way). The term “**digital assets**” often occurs in the OAIS model (see Appendix 1) as a more generic term, including research data.

1.2.2 LTP Principles

The principles of long-term preservation go back to at least January 2007³. Current principles for LTP, such as the TRUST principles (see below), are founded on and an elaboration of this origin. The 2007 principles were formulated as ten basic characteristics of digital preservation repositories:

A long term preservation repository ...

1. (...) commits to continuing maintenance of digital objects for (an) identified community/communities.

² http://www.sodataglossary.shoutwiki.com/wiki/Research_data

³ The principles were formulated by representatives of four leading preservation organizations:

- [The Digital Curation Center](#) (UK)
- [Digital Preservation Europe](#) (DPE, a European consortium of libraries, archives and university institutions)
- [NESTOR](#) (Germany)
- [Center for Research Libraries](#) (North America)

2. (...) demonstrates organizational fitness (including financial, staffing, and processes) to fulfill its commitment.
3. (...) acquires and maintains requisite contractual and legal rights and fulfills responsibilities.
4. (...) has an effective and efficient policy [framework]⁴.
5. (...) acquires and ingests digital objects based upon stated criteria that correspond to its commitments and capabilities.
6. (...) ensures the integrity, authenticity and usability of digital objects it holds over time.
7. (...) creates and maintains requisite metadata about the provenance⁵ of digital objects it holds and about actions taken on them during preservation.
8. (...) fulfills requisite dissemination requirements.
9. (...) has a strategic program for preservation planning and action.
10. (...) has technical infrastructure adequate to continuing maintenance and security of its digital objects.

Some formulations in these principles raise questions. Including the following:

Ad 1: What is/are “identified [or designated] community/communities”?

Ad 5: What are “stated criteria” for data acquisition?

Ad 7: What is “requisite metadata”?

These questions address respectively for whom (the target audience), what and how (well described) digital objects are preserved. The subject of “designated communities” is discussed in section 1.3.2 below. The criteria for acquisition are obviously related to the target audience and it also influences the way and degree of detail in which data are described. Anyhow, a LTP Policy should reflect these principles, and organizations offering services to preserve data for the long term should take these principles seriously.

The five TRUST principles for digital repositories, formulated in 2020 as a Community Effort and endorsed by the international Research Data Alliance, read as follows:

Principle	Guidance for Repositories
Transparency	To be transparent about specific repository services and data holdings that are verifiable by publicly accessible evidence.
Responsibility	To be responsible for ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data holdings and for the reliability and persistence of its service.
User Focus	To ensure that the data management norms and expectations of target user communities are met.
Sustainability	To sustain services and preserve data holdings for the long-term.
Technology	To provide infrastructure and capabilities to support secure, persistent, and reliable services.

Source: Lin et al., 2020. The TRUST Principles for Digital Repositories. Scientific Data. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

⁴ See Appendix 4 for the term “policy framework”.

⁵ Described as “the relevant production, access support, and usage process contexts before preservation”.

1.2.3 Areas to be covered in a LTP Policy

There are many good practice documents that try to provide guidance on which areas to cover in a Digital Preservation Plan or LTP Policy, such as those by the [British Library](#) and the [National Archives](#) in the UK, or those by the [Library of Congress](#) and [National Archives](#) in the US. There were also recommendations by specific digital preservation projects, of which the InterPARES projects⁶ (that started in 1999) was particularly influential. ERPAnet (Electronic Resource Preservation and Access Network) was another leading group that formulated guidelines in the 2000s. Such recommendations, handbooks and other online resources were usefully summarized by the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) in the UK. According to the DPC, a Digital Preservation Policy describes an “organisation’s aims and objectives about the long-term care of digital objects”, specifying⁷:

- Preservation strategies and acceptable actions
- Decisions about the digital objects (formats, metadata)
- Standards
- Who the material is being preserved for
- Resourcing
- Responsibilities

Perhaps the most extensive and detailed recommendations for a LTP Policy are provided by the reference model for Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS, [ISO 14721:2012](#)), published in 2012 (“Purple book”) and updated in 2020 (“Pink book”)⁸. The OAIS model organizes a model archival system in terms of functional entities:

- Ingest
- Data Management
- Archival Storage
- Preservation Planning
- Administration
- Access

A brief overview of the OAIS reference model is provided in [Appendix 1](#). The LTP Policy Template we present here follows the OAIS functional entities.

There are also commercial guidelines and tools available for digital preservation, and companies such as Artefactual Systems Inc., the main developer of the open source digital preservation system Archivematica, also provide guidelines for digital preservation policies and good practices (see, for example, [Preservation Planning | Documentation \(Archivematica 1.13.2\)](#)).

Many organisations with a responsibility for digital preservation have formulated their digital preservation strategies and LTP policies. In most policies, references are given to the legal and regulatory frameworks in which the organisation operates, and to relevant standards, certifications and other guidelines. Obviously, the Preservation Plan by Data Archiving and

⁶ See: <http://www.interpares.org>

⁷ See: <https://www.dpconline.org/docs/miscellaneous/training/1719-mp-policy/file>

⁸ CCSDS, Recommendation for Space Data System Practices. Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS). Recommended Practice CCSDS 650.0-M-2, Magenta Book [also known as “Purple Book”], CCSDS Secretariat (NASA), Washington, DC, June 2012: <https://public.ccsds.org/pubs/650x0m2.pdf>; update October 2020 (draft): <https://public.ccsds.org/Lists/CCSDS%206500P21/650x0021.pdf>.

Networked Services (DANS, Version 1.0 - May 2018; currently being updated: Preservation plan | DANS), which entails both a preservation strategy and a policy, is important here. A good model of a preservation policy is provided by the UK Data Archive (version 12.00, 26 January 2021), see: [UK Data Archive Preservation Policy](#).

To wrap up, perhaps the most fundamental element of any LTP Policy is a mission or dedication by an organisation to keep digital assets alive. And in order to guarantee that, the organisation itself must be sustainable.

1.3 Applying the LTP Policy Template

1.3.1 Some considerations when outsourcing LTP

If a data repository outsources LTP to a dedicated archive (LTP Institution), there may still be functions the repository will want to take responsibility for that are normally included in a digital preservation plan, in particular:

- Activities related to the *ingest* of digital assets uploaded by researchers to a repository, including the metadata describing these assets.
- Activities related to the *access* of digital assets stored in the repository, including access agreements and licenses, *for as long as the materials exist in the repository (or as long as the repository itself exists)*.

If for any reason a repository service will be discontinued, the ingest of new materials will automatically stop; however, the continued access to the assets in the repository, which have been archived at [LTP Institution], should from then on be taken care of by the [LTP Service].

The repository service needs to indicate whether it wants the data it holds to be findable (and hence visible) to the outside world via the [LTP service] or not.

- If this is the case (data findable/visible), the [LTP Service] will make the metadata available through its search mechanism, but it will refer for access to the data via a persistent reference.
- If this is not the case, the [LTP Service] is a “dark archive” and metadata will not be exposed and hence not be findable in the [LTP Service], which situation will only change when the repository service will no longer provide access, for instance because it ceases to exist. Then, the [LTP Service] will make the metadata available through its search mechanism and will provide access to users, according to the access policy.

In case LTP is outsourced by a repository to a dedicated external archive, one or more additional contracts will be needed between both organisations.

- The LTP Policy should be accompanied by a Long-Term Preservation Agreement (LTP Agreement) between the repository and the LTP archive if datasets are transferred from a data repository to an external, dedicated LTP archive. The process by which data and metadata are transferred to the [LTP service] (usually automated and in bulk) should be described in this LTP Agreement.
- In case personal data is involved in the transfer of data to an external LTP Service, the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR; see Appendix 3 on legal and statutory requirements) requires the signing of an additional Data Processing Agreement (DPA) between the organisations transferring the data.⁹

⁹ A generic template of a DPA is available: <https://gdpr.eu/data-processing-agreement/>

- How the costs of the LTP Service are covered can best be specified in a separate cost statement as an annex to the LTP Agreement.

1.3.2 The designated community or communities

An issue that needs special consideration is the definition of the designated community or communities. The research (or scientific, or scholarly) community is defined as a diverse network of interacting scientists and scholars. It includes many "sub-communities" working on particular scientific/scholarly fields of research, and within particular institutions; although many research communities are distinguished on the basis of disciplinary boundaries, interdisciplinary and cross-institutional activities are also significant. In this context, research communities contribute to a certain volume of digital research data of relevance for that community.

Many repository services are intended for a varied audience:

- For individual researchers as well as scientific communities.
- For professional and citizen scientists.
- For research data and software of various sizes.
- From diverse contexts and disciplines.

The first of the ten preservation principles (see section 2.2.3) states that a LTP repository should commit "to continuing maintenance of digital objects for identified community/communities". This principle returns in several requirements of the CoreTrustSeal (CTS), which repeatedly stresses that the needs of the "Designated Community" are to be known, respected and served.

It is a matter of debate how specific the community needs to be described to serve their requirements sufficiently. Both the principles and the CTS make the assumption that LTP Repositories serve well-defined communities, and indeed, many repositories serve, for instance, specific disciplines. Admittedly, particular data types are used in particular ways by particular communities, which may have consequences for their treatment in repositories: they may, for instance, require special metadata elements to be described adequately.

Yet, many discipline-independent and institutional repositories are set up for a broad range of scientific and scholarly uses. The characteristics and needs of a diversity of scientific communities were incorporated in the design and functionality of the service.

Moreover, according to the OAIS Reference Model, the Designated Community for an OAIS service is identified as an "identified group of potential Consumers who should be able to understand a particular set of information. The Designated Community may be composed of multiple user communities. A Designated Community is defined by the Archive and this definition may change over time."

According to the same ISO standard 14721:2012, a Consumer is defined as "the role played by those persons, or client systems, who interact with OAIS services to find preserved information of interest and to access that information in detail. This can include other OAISes, as well as internal OAIS persons or systems."

It is obvious that a LTP archive inherits the researchers and communities served by repositories outsourcing the LTP function by proxy.

1.3.3 The LTP Policy Template and Curation Levels

In the CoreTrustSeal (CTS) [Requirements for Trustworthy Digital Repositories](#), CTS distinguishes between four levels of curation that can be performed and should be selected in the certification process. These are:

- A. Content distributed as deposited.
- B. Basic curation – e.g., brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation.
- C. Enhanced curation – e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation.
- D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy.

The relationship between these curation levels and the relevant LTP Template sections are summarised in Table 1. The table indicates which LTP Policy articles are needed to comply with the different curation levels. The table only comprises those articles that are directly relevant for digital curation. A distinction of “in-house”(2A) and “outsourced”(2B) LTP is also made. An empty cell indicates that the article is not needed for this curation level, whereas an ‘x’ marks that the article is needed for compliance with the corresponding curation level.

Table 1. LTP Policy Template sections and curation levels

Policy Section and Article		Brief description	Curation Level			
			A: Bit preservation	B: Basic Curation	C: Enhanced Curation	D: Data-level curation
2. Ingest						
2A. LTP in-house	2B. LTP outsourced					
2.1	2.6	Submission Information Package for Ingest	x	x	x	x
2.2	2.7	Metadata index and Cataloguing		x	x	x
2.3	2.8	Licenses		x	x	x
2.4	2.9	Persistent Identifiers		x	x	x
	2.10	Additional PIDs		x	x	x
2.5	2.11	Quality control	none	basic checks of metadata	enhanced checks of metadata	enhanced checks of data and metadata
2.5.1	2.11.1	Metadata supplied by depositor		x	x	x
2.5.2	2.11.2	Ingest control	none	basic	enhanced	enhanced
	2.11.3	Mapping of metadata		x	x	x
2.5.3	2.11.4	Required metadata fields	none	basic	extended	full
2.5.4	2.11.5	Responsibility for metadata		x	x	x

2.5.5	2.11.6	Notification of deficient metadata			x	x
2.5.6	2.11.7	Data and metadata corrections			x	x
3. Archival Storage						
3.1		Archival actions and chain of provenance	none	basic	extended	full
3.2		Archival storage of AIPs	x	x	x	x
3.4		Integrity and security measures	checksums	basic	extended	extended
4. Data Management						
4.1		Metadata catalogue maintenance		x	x	x
4.2		Archival metadata supporting version control	x	x	x	x
4.3.1		Derived and dissemination formats			x	x
4.3.2		Authenticity and integrity of AIPs	x	x	x	x
4.3.3		Documentation of chain of custody		x	x	x
4.4		Preferred and accepted file formats			x	x
4.5		Obsolescence of file formats				x
4.6.1		Migration of preferred formats				x
4.6.2		Preserving outdated formats				x
4.7		Deletion of datasets and files		x	x	x
4.8		Tombstone records for deleted datasets	x	x	x	x
6. Preservation Planning						
6.1		Monitoring the content of the [LTP Service]	x	x	x	x
6.2		Reviewing and updating list of preferred formats			x	x
6.3		Other monitoring for preservation planning		x	x	x

1.4 Cost modelling for LTP

1.4.1 LTP Costs and business models

For smaller datasets (sometimes called “long-tail data”) in curated repositories, the majority of the costs for long-term preservation typically arise during the ingest phase of research data into the LTP Service, during which the checking of metadata quality can be an important cost factor.

In many repositories that are not (intensively) curated, the responsibility for the quality of the data descriptions and documentation lies primarily with the researchers or research communities owning the data. In the LTP Policy Template, the amount of checking performed

by the LTP Service depends on the level of curation offered by the Service, as reflected in Table 1.

Storage costs are a second main factor in digital preservation, and these obviously return yearly. In repositories that are mainly geared towards the preservation of “long-tail data” (which are relatively small to modest in size), the storage costs are a less important factor than for “big data” repositories.

In repositories which are dealing with bigger data volumes, the costs of storage for the long-term are considerable, and the core questions to be answered for a LTP strategy are in the business model and in the selection of the data that need archiving. Without a business model in which storage costs are covered, any LTP Policy for big data repositories are bound to fail. “How to recover the costs for the preservation of data in the long-term? And who pays for what?” are the core questions to be answered.

1.4.2 Cost models for LTP

Over the years, a variety of studies, projects and reports on the costs of long-term preservation have been performed or produced¹⁰. It is unfeasible to provide an extensive overview of the literature on the subject here. Many different cost models have been proposed and described. We summarize the most important and well-known of them in Table 2.

Table 2. Overview of cost models for digital preservation

ID	Name	Acronym	Owner	Authors (year)
1	Test bed Cost Model for Digital Preservation	T-CMDP	National Archives of the Netherlands	Kejser et al. (2011)
2	NASA Cost Estimation Tool	NASA-CET	National Aeronautics & Space Administration (NASA)	Hendley (1998)
3	LIFE3 Costing Model	LIFE3	University College London and the British Library	Wheatley et al. (2009)
4	Keeping Research Data Safe	KRDS	Charles Beagrie Ltd	Stanger (2011)
5	Cost Model for Digital Archiving	CMDA	Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS)	Palaiologk et al. (2012)

¹⁰ An overview of cost projects for digital preservation is provided by the EU-funded 4C-project: <https://www.4cproject.eu/community-resources/related-projects/>

6	Cost Model for Digital Preservation	CMDP	Danish National Archives and the Danish Royal Library	Kejser et al. (2012)
7	DP4LIB Cost Model	DP4LIB	The German National Library	DP4Lib (2013)
8	PrestoPRIME Cost model for Digital Storage	PP-CMDS	The PrestoPRIME Project	PrestoPRIME (2011)
9	Total Cost of Preservation	CDL-TCP	California Digital Library	University of California (2013)
10	Economic Model of Long-Term Storage	EMLTS	David Rosenthal	Rosenthal et al. (2011/2012)
11	Digital Curation Sustainability Model	DCSM	4C Project	Grindley (2015)
12	ENSURE Cost Model for Long-Term Digital Preservation	ENSURE	ENSURE (EC FP7 project)	Xue et al. (2011)
13	Dutch Cost Model for Digital Preservation	DCMDP	Nationale Coalitie Digitale Duurzaamheid (NCDD)	Uffen et al. (2017, 2019)

Adapted (and extended) from the [Summary of Cost Models](#) by <http://www.4cproject.eu>

There is a certain correspondence on the cost categories the various models discern, and which factors are contributing to the total costs of digital preservation, but at the same time there appears to be a great variety of the ways in which these costs are calculated in practice. The actual costs will largely depend:

- on the volumes of content to be preserved
- on the curation level that is offered by the LTP service provider
- on the organisational context, funding situation and charging policy of the LTP service provider
- on whether or not the digital preservation is outsourced (and which choice is made with respect to provision of access, including user support)

Where LTP is outsourced, it is practical to include a cost statement as part of the LTP agreement annexed to the LTP Policy.

Part II: LTP Policy Template

Long-Term Preservation Policy Template

Contents

1. Objectives, scope and delimitation of this policy
2. Ingest
3. Archival Storage
4. Data Management
5. Administration
6. Preservation Planning
7. Access

1. Objectives, scope and delimitation of this policy

- 1.1. The general aim of this preservation policy is to ensure the authentic and trustworthy preservation and accessibility of digital research data and related outputs, henceforth referred to as “datasets”, for reuse in the long term.
- 1.2. The specific aims of the preservation policy are to:
 - Provide authentic and reliable instances of datasets to researchers;
 - Maintain the integrity and quality of the datasets;
 - Ensure that datasets are managed throughout their lifecycle (e.g. when migrations or changes in metadata are carried out) in the medium that is most appropriate for the task they perform;
 - Ensure that the relevant level of information security is applied to each dataset;
- 1.3. The scope of this policy is limited to [LTP Institution]’s service for long-term preservation, [LTP Service]. It applies exclusively to datasets held in [LTP Service]. This policy does not consider preservation of other materials, such as [LTP Institution]’s web pages, internal and external documents, and digital objects in any other services the [LTP Institution] provides.
- 1.4. The [LTP Institution] assumes responsibility for the long-term preservation and accessibility of datasets ingested (by individual deposits or bulk data transfers) into its [LTP Service].
- 1.5. Long-term preservation and provision of sustained access to datasets fits within the remit and mission of [LTP Institution].
- 1.6. The length of the preservation period is ... <specify the preservation period in years or “indefinite”>, unless legal obligations prevent this (as described in article 4.7).

- 1.7. [LTP Service] is designed to preserve data in a way that can be assessed by and is useful for the designated communities it intends to serve. This target audience consists of ... <specify the designated communities, such as scientific domains, research communities, or research in general>.

2. Ingest

This section distinguishes two situations, to which partly different articles apply:

- A. [LTP Service] is provided by the repository or data service itself. In this situation, the ingest takes place via deposits by researchers or research communities into the repository, which also acts as [LTP Service]. Researchers or research communities are the depositors.
- B. [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution]. In this situation, the ingest consists of (bulk) data transfers from the repository to the external [LTP Service]. The repository/data service acts as the depositor on behalf of the researchers and research communities, who originally deposited the datasets. A Long-Term Preservation Agreement (LTP Agreement) describing the particulars of the responsibilities of both parties involved will be necessary.

Note that the choice between situation A and B also has repercussions for the ways in which the access to datasets will be arranged (see section 7). For further considerations on outsourcing LTP refer to section 1.3.1 of the report.

2A. [LTP Service] is provided by the data service itself

- 2.1. The datasets, including metadata as supplied by the depositor [= researcher or research community], are considered by [LTP service] as the Submission Information Package (SIP) in OAIS terms. This is the "original" information to be stored for long-term preservation.
- 2.2. The datasets are professionally cataloged according to the metadata standard used by [LTP Service].
- 2.3. [LTP Service] supports a list of licenses for open data sharing, from which a selection can be made by the depositor during ingestion. A list of supported licenses is available [provide reference; for an example see Appendix 6].
- 2.4. [LTP Service] provides a Persistent Identifier [PID] to each ingested [dataset / file / object] <indicate to which units the PID apply> for long-term reference to their location.
- 2.5. The quality control of the metadata is maintained as follows:
 - The datasets that the [LTP Service] ingests are accompanied by metadata as supplied by the [Depositor], which should be adequate to enable the designated communities to understand and reuse the content for analytical and research purposes.

- The deposited datasets (including metadata) are checked and validated by [LTP service] according to documented data ingest procedures, including the following checks <indicate what applies>:
 - Virus scans
 - Completeness of data (e.g. checksums)
 - Metadata and additional documentation
 - Compliance with preferred / accepted formats
 - Organisation of data (data structure), reformatting
 - Presence of personal data
 - Data cleaning
 - Other: ... <specify>
- In order to guarantee minimal metadata quality, only records that comply with the following basic Dublin Core Metadata Terms¹¹ can be successfully ingested into [LTP Service] <indicate which terms minimally apply>:
 - Title
 - Creator
 - Description
 - Date (created)
 - Rights
 - Audience
 - ... <specify more terms if applicable>
- The completeness and accuracy of the metadata accompanying the deposited dataset is the responsibility of the depositor.
- [LTP Service] may notify the depositor of deficiencies and inaccuracies in the metadata (during or after ingestion).
- Alternatively, if datasets or metadata contain deficiencies, [LTP Service] can make alterations post ingest. Hereby distinction is made between minor and major alterations to digital assets:
 - Major: when a digital object in a dataset is changed, this will result in a new version and therefore a new dataset with a new PID in [LTP service]. The new and the old version are cross-referenced in their respective descriptive metadata, and the new version will be the default version for access.
 - Minor: when there is a change (addition or edit) in the metadata, descriptive documents or supplementary files, this is documented in the (administrative) metadata, no new dataset is created and no new persistent identifier is minted.

¹¹ See DCMI terms: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

2B. [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution]

- 2.6. The datasets, including metadata as supplied by depositor [= data service], are considered by [LTP service] as the Submission Information Package (SIP) in OAIS terms. This is the “original” information to be stored for long-term preservation in the [LTP Service].
- 2.7. The datasets are professionally catalogued according to the metadata standard used by [LTP Service].
- 2.8. Licenses for open data sharing attributed to the datasets are ingested “as is”, and are preserved and supported unchanged by [LTP service]. A list of supported licenses is available [provide reference; for an example see Appendix 6].
- 2.9. Persistent Identifiers [PIDs] minted by the [data service] are ingested into the [LTP Service] “as is”, and continue to refer to the original location of the data (see section 7 on Access for changes in the case [data service] ceases to exist).
- 2.10. [LTP Service] will allocate additional PIDs for reference to archived copies of the data sets in [LTP Service] (see section 7 on Access for alternatives in referencing for access to datasets).
- 2.11. The quality control of the metadata is maintained as follows:
- The datasets that the [LTP Service] ingests are accompanied by metadata as supplied by the [Depositor], which should be adequate to enable the designated communities to understand and reuse the content for analytical and research purposes.
 - The deposited datasets (including metadata) are checked and validated by [LTP service] according to documented data ingest procedures, including the following checks <indicate what applies>:
 - Virus scans
 - Completeness of data (e.g. checksums)
 - Metadata and additional documentation
 - Compliance with preferred / accepted formats
 - Organisation of data (data structure), reformatting
 - Presence of personal data
 - Data cleaning
 - Other: ... <specify>
 - Metadata fields of the [data service] are mapped with the fields of the [LTP Service] metadata schema:
 - Corresponding fields (from the same metadata scheme) are copied
 - Similar fields (from different metadata schemes) are mapped wherever possible
 - Fields that cannot be mapped are stored with the dataset as additional documentation (in a separate metadata blob file).

- In order to guarantee minimal metadata quality, only datasets that comply with the following basic Dublin Core Metadata Terms¹² can be successfully ingested into [LTP Service] <indicate which terms minimally apply>:
 - Title
 - Creator
 - Description
 - Date (created)
 - Rights
 - Audience
 - ... <specify more terms if desired>
- The completeness and accuracy of the metadata ingested from [data service] into [LTP Service] is the responsibility of the [data service].
- [LTP Service] may notify the [data service] of deficiencies and inaccuracies in the metadata (during or after ingestion).
- Alternatively, if datasets or metadata contain deficiencies, [LTP Service] can make alterations post ingest. Hereby distinction is made between minor and major alterations to digital assets:
 - Major: when a digital object in a dataset is changed, this will result in a new version and therefore a new dataset with a new PID in [LTP service]. The new and the old version are cross-referenced in their respective descriptive metadata, and the new version will be the default version for access.
 - Minor: when there is a change (addition or edit) in the metadata, descriptive documents or supplementary files, this is documented in the (administrative) metadata, no new dataset is created and no new persistent identifier is minted.

3. Archival Storage

- 3.1. The ingested datasets (data and metadata) constitute the basis for the Archival Information Package (AIP) in OAIS terms. Archival actions related to the custody of AIPs, which may affect the chain of provenance, will be documented, including changes in <indicate what applies>:
 - ... the archival system (upgrades, new systems)
 - ... documentation standards
 - ... license definitions
 - ... file formats (format conversions and updates)
 - ... storage location (migrations to other facilities)
 - ... other <specify other archival actions influencing the chain of provenance>
- 3.2. The archival storage function receives AIPs from the ingest function and adds them to the permanent storage facility, and oversees the management of this storage, including

¹² See DCMI terms: <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/dublin-core/dcmi-terms/>

media monitoring and refreshment. This ensures that AIPs will be retrievable and can be disseminated over time.

- 3.3. [LTP Service] does not assume responsibility for the preservation of data that are hosted externally, unless this is specifically agreed with an external storage provider, to be specified in an agreement (as in article 3.5).
- 3.4. The [LTP Institution] is committed to take all necessary precautions to ensure the physical integrity and security of the datasets stored in its [LTP Service], including <indicate which measures apply>:
 - Periodic technology-vulnerability scans
 - SLAs with external IT providers, e.g. for data storage
 - Procedures for file fixity checking (checksums), verifying that data have not been altered or corrupted
 - A confidentiality statement for [LTP Service] staff (as described in article 6.6.4)
 - Periodic security audits
 - Other measures: ... <specify>
- 3.5. [LTP Institution] may outsource the physical data storage to an external storage provider, provided it has a contract and accompanying Service Level Agreement (SLA) with its provider, which include <indicate what applies>:
 - A confidentiality statement
 - A quality assurance guarantee (see also article 2.6).
 - An information security policy and security measures.
 - Error checking routines and error solving procedures.
 - A disaster recovery procedure.
 - A monitoring policy of servers and storage media, and the timely refreshment of media.
 - A performance reporting mechanism.
 - A backup policy.
 - Storage of at least two copies in physically and geographically different locations.
 - Other: ... <specify>

4. Data Management

- 4.1. [LTP Service] maintains a catalogue of metadata which uses a standard schema for describing its contents. This database is searchable by internal and external finding aids.
- 4.2. The Archival Information Package includes administrative metadata which support archival operations, including change or version control of datasets.
- 4.3. [LTP Institution] guarantees the timeliness, authenticity and integrity of the datasets in its [LTP Service] for future access and reuse.

- The datasets (and metadata) ingested (including exact and integral copies thereof) are considered as „original“ and authentic.
 - If preservation and/or dissemination copies in derived formats are made (e.g. preserved formats or lower resolution video formats for web viewing), these will be stored alongside the originals.
 - Provenance information is supplied for all copies in preservation and dissemination formats that can be traced back to the original datasets as ingested.

 - Authenticity and integrity of Archival Information Packages (AIPs) imply that once a dataset is ingested into the [LTP Service], the AIP can not be changed or removed by the user.
 - Only authorized staff of [LTP Institution] have the right to modify the format and/or functionality of an archived object, if this is deemed necessary to facilitate the digital sustainability, distribution or re-use of the information it contains.
 - [LTP Institution] ensures that any alteration to the preserved version of any part of a dataset will only take place under controlled conditions and will be accurately documented. Hence, the content stored in [LTP Service] is of a static nature.
 - When datasets are updated, changed or extended, the resulting new versions are considered and treated as new assets.

 - The chain of custody of datasets archived in the [LTP Service] is documented through metadata, which guarantee that all archival actions are explicit, complete, correct and current.
- 4.4. [LTP Service] maintains (or conforms to) a documented list of <indicate what applies>:
- ... preferred or archival formats, about which [LTP Service] is dedicated to offer long-term guarantees in terms of future findability, accessibility and reusability¹³.
 - ... accepted formats, which are preserved in the format as ingested, for which the findability and accessibility are guaranteed, but for which the future reusability can not be guaranteed.
- 4.5. [LTP Service] monitors the potential obsolescence of file formats and has conversion policies and procedures in place to take action when required.
- 4.6. In case of conversion of objects to another (preferred or archival) file format (e.g. for preservation or access purposes), the [LTP Service] will also maintain the original file(s) <indicate what applies>:

¹³ The Interoperability of datasets depends on characteristics of the data that are partly beyond the control of [LTP service] and can therefore not be guaranteed by [LTP Service]. The Interoperability of research data is the responsibility of the researcher / research community.

- Files stored in the [LTP Service] from outdated formats are migrated to successor formats, and the archival metadata is updated accordingly.
 - Files in outdated formats are preserved to maintain the chain of provenance.
- 4.7. Datasets or files that are archived, published and/or exposed in the [LTP Service] can only be deleted or made inaccessible by [LTP Institution]'s authorized staff for compelling reasons:
- If the content is unlawful.
 - If there is a legally binding maximum preservation period for the content.
 - If personal data appears to be preserved without permission of research subjects.
 - If the content consists of personal data, and a research subject rightfully objects to the preservation of a digital object with an appeal to the GDPR (e.g. right to be forgotten; or revocation of informed consent).
 - Other compelling reasons, to be decided by the director of the [LTP Institution].
- 4.8. In case a data object needs to be deleted, this is recorded in the metadata, which will continue to exist as a "tombstone" record.

5. Administration¹⁴

- 5.1. [LTP Institution] monitors the operations of its [LTP Service] and publishes periodic reports on its performance. [An example of a monitoring schedule is provided in Appendix 2].
- 5.2. [LTP Institution] develops a multi-annual strategy which includes the strategic direction and upgrading of the [LTP Service].
- 5.3. The planning and control cycle of [LTP Institution] is overseen by ... <specify how or by whom the planning and control cycle is monitored>.
- 5.4. The strategy and functioning of [LTP Institution] is subject to periodic external evaluations, the reports of which are available publicly / on request / otherwise: ... <specify what applies>.
- 5.5. A(n) (scientific) advisory board consisting of prominent members of the designated community advises [LTP Institution] on its strategic course and development.
- 5.6. [LTP Institution] maintains functions for providing customer support.
- 5.7. [LTP Institution] maintains a publicly available list and description of legal and statutory regulations which apply (see Appendix 3 for an overview of generally applicable European and national laws and regulations; select which specific regulations apply):

¹⁴ Note that several Administrative functions of the OAIS model are dealt with in other sections of this policy:

- General Terms and Conditions of Use
- Data Deposit Agreement
- Long-Term Preservation Agreement
- Data Processing Agreements
- User licenses
- Privacy policy
- Liability statement
- Ownership rights statement
- Other applicable regulations: ... <specify>

6. Preservation Planning

- 6.1. [LTP Institution] monitors the contents of its [LTP Service] and periodically publishes metrics on key performance indicators.
- 6.2. [LTP Institution] reviews its preferred and/or accepted formats list and guidelines periodically for obsolescence and completeness, updating and extending them as needed.
- 6.3. [LTP Institution] performs the following other monitoring functions for preservation planning <indicate which monitoring activities apply>:
 - Monitoring security risks, in order to anticipate and control such risks.
 - Technology watch, in order to recommend adaptations in its technology environment, in particular its archival system(s).
 - Monitoring changes in service requirements of its Designated Communities.
 - Other monitoring activities: ... <specify>
- 6.4. Roles and responsibilities, confidentiality, limited liability <indicate what applies>:
 - The Director of [LTP Institution] is responsible for maintaining this policy.
 - The staff of [LTP Institution] implements this policy as appropriate to their roles and responsibilities.
 - Preservation decisions about the [LTP Service] are made within the context of the [LTP Institution]'s mission and strategy, balancing the constraints of costs, scholarly value, user accessibility, and legal admissibility.
 - [LTP Institution]'s staff, including temporary staff, trainees, (visiting) fellows and volunteers, are accountable for keeping confidentiality when processing digital assets stored in [LTP Service], in particular personal data, in any way whatsoever, by signing a confidentiality statement.
 - This policy will be evaluated and, if necessary, will be revised every ... years <specify the evaluation and revision cycle>, or as soon as security threats, changes in technology or legal and statutory context require to do so.
 - [LTP Institution] is not liable for the contents, including errors, of research data ingested into its [LTP Service], nor for (possible errors in) the metadata and additional documentation associated with those datasets. [LTP Institution] is

also not liable for incorrect inferences resulting from the analysis of those datasets.

6.5. Funding and contingency plan:

- [LTP Institution] declares it receives adequate funding to fulfil its mission, which includes the maintenance of the [LTP Service].
- In case of dissolution of the [LTP Institution], it has a continuity plan in place which guarantees that a successor organization will take over the care of the [LTP service]¹⁵.

7. Access

As in the Ingest section (2), this section distinguishes two different situations, to which partly different articles apply:

- A. [LTP Service] is provided by the [data service] itself. In this situation, the access takes place through access mechanisms of the [Data Service].
- B. [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution]. In this situation, the [data service] needs to indicate in the LTP Agreement whether it wants the datasets in [LTP Service] to be exposed (= to be findable and/or accessible) for end users via the [LTP Service] or not.

If for any reason the original [data service] is discontinued, the access function to the datasets of [data service], as ingested and preserved by [LTP Institution], will be taken over by the [LTP Service]. In this situation two extra articles apply (7.6 and 7.7).

7.1. [LTP Service] provides the following access functions <indicate what applies>:

- A user interface for browsing and searching its content
- An API using an open and universal protocol (e.g. OAI-PMH: Open Archives Initiative: Protocol for Metadata Harvesting)
- Other: ... <specify>

¹⁵ This is in conformance to the mandatory OAIS requirements and CTS requirement 3 “Continuity of access: The repository has a continuity plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its holdings”. For example, in the case of DANS: The NWO-KNAW *Samenwerkingsovereenkomst DANS* (Collaboration Agreement DANS) 2015 explicitly states that, in the case of discontinuity of DANS, NWO and KNAW will take over the responsibility for the digital assets archived at DANS and store these elsewhere “in the most responsible manner possible and under equivalent technical conditions” (article 10.6 of the Collaboration Agreement).

- 7.2. Metadata in [LTP Service] are always openly accessible, i.e. without copy- or database-rights and without authentication or authorisation of users (either through the user interface or via the API).
- 7.3. Users need to register (create an account) and to login to the [LTP Service] if the license to view and download files requires them to do so.
- 7.4. Authentication by registration and logging in is not obligatory for viewing or downloading data with licences equivalent to full Open Access (CC0 Waiver).
- 7.5. In order to enable reuse, data released from [LTP Service] are always accompanied by <indicate what applies>:
- A clear conditions of use statement conforming to the applicable licence or CC0 waiver.
 - A standard citation recommendation to encourage proper data citation.
 - Other: ... <specify>

Article 7.6 and 7.7 only apply in case [LTP Service] is provided by an external organisation / separate [LTP Institution] as described under situation B in the text box above.

- 7.6. By default, as long as the [data service] exists and its content is accessible for end users, the standard PID assigned by [data service] to a dataset archived in the [LTP Service] refers to the location in the original [data service].
- 7.7. In case the [data service] ceases to exist and becomes inaccessible for end users, the access to the datasets stored at the [LTP Service] will become findable and accessible via the search and download functions of [LTP Service], under similar access conditions and licenses as in the original [data service].

Part III: Appendices

Appendix 1. Summary of the OAIS Reference Model

The LTP Policy Template follows the recommendations of the [Open Archival Information System \(OAIS\) reference model](#). In spite of the fact that the report in which the OAIS model is described is called “recommended practice”, it nevertheless contains a section of “mandatory responsibilities” that an organization wishing to operate as an OAIS Archive must fulfil:

Mandatory responsibilities

An OAIS Archive shall:

- Negotiate for and accept appropriate information from information Producers.
- Obtain sufficient control of the information provided to the level needed to ensure Long Term Preservation.
- Determine, either by itself or in conjunction with other parties, which entities should become the Designated Community, that is, the communities that should be able to understand the information provided. Definition of the Designated Community includes a determination of their Knowledge Base.
- Ensure that the information to be preserved is Independently Understandable to the Designated Community. In particular, the Designated Community should be able to understand the information without needing special resources such as the assistance of the experts who produced the information.
- Follow documented policies and procedures which ensure that the information is preserved against all reasonable contingencies, including the demise of the Archive, ensuring that it is never deleted unless allowed as part of an approved strategy. There should be no ad-hoc deletions.
- Make the preserved information available to the Designated Community and enable the information to be disseminated as copies of, or as traceable to, the original submitted Content Information with evidence supporting its Authenticity.

The reference model

The OAIS reference model is depicted in Figure 1. Our description of the six functional entities is based on this OAIS model, from which the definitions and summaries below have been derived¹⁶.

¹⁶ CCSDS, Recommendation for Space Data System Practices. Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS). Recommended Practice CCSDS 650.0-M-2, Magenta Book [also known as “Purple Book”], CCSDS Secretariat (NASA), Washington, DC, June 2012.

Figure 1. OAIS Functional Entities

Selected OAIS Definitions (slightly adapted for use in this document)

The definitions below are taken from the OAIS "Purple Book", with minor modifications or clarifications to fit the purposes of this document¹⁷.

- Archive:** An organization that intends and has accepted the responsibility to preserve information for access and use by a Designated Community. The people and systems working for the Archive may be part of a larger organization. If an Archive meets the responsibilities recommended by the OAIS reference model, it can be called an "OAIS Archive". The term 'Open' in OAIS is used to imply that the recommendations and standards are developed in open forums, and it does not imply that access to the Archive is unrestricted. **Note:** in this document [LTP Service] is synonymous to "(OAIS) Archive", whereas [LTP Institution] is the larger organisation to which the [LTP Service] belongs.
- (Data) Producer:** The role played by those persons or client systems that provide the information to be preserved.

¹⁷ CCSDS, Recommendation for Space Data System Practices. Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS). Recommended Practice CCSDS 650.0-M-2, Magenta Book [commonly referred to as the "Purple Book"], CCSDS Secretariat (NASA), Washington, DC, June 2012: <https://public.ccsds.org/pubs/650x0m2.pdf>; update October 2020 (draft, also called the "Pink Book"): <https://public.ccsds.org/Lists/CCSDS%206500P21/650x0021.pdf>.

- **(Data) Consumer:** The role played by those persons, or client systems, who interact with archival services to find preserved information of interest and to access that information in detail.
- **Submission Information Package (SIP):** An Information Package that is delivered by the Producer to the Archive for use in the construction or update of one or more AIPs and/or the associated Descriptive Information.
- **Archival Information Package (AIP):** An Information Package, consisting of the Content Information and the associated Preservation Description Information (PDI), which is preserved within an Archive.
- **Dissemination Information Package (DIP):** An Information Package, derived from one or more AIPs, and sent by Archives to the Consumer in response to a request to the Archive.
- **Preservation Description Information (PDI):** The information which is necessary for adequate preservation of the Content Information and which can be categorized as Provenance, Reference, Fixity, Context, and Access Rights Information.
- **Designated Community:** An identified group of potential Consumers who should be able to understand a particular set of information. The Designated Community may be composed of multiple user communities. A Designated Community is defined by the Archive and this definition may change over time.
- **Authenticity:** The degree to which a person (or system) regards an object as what it is purported to be. Authenticity is judged on the basis of evidence.
- **Dissemination Information Package (DIP):** An Information Package, derived from one or more AIPs, and sent by Archives to the Consumer in response to a request to the Archive.
- **Long Term:** A period of time long enough for there to be concern about the impacts of changing technologies, including support for new media and data formats, and of a changing Designated Community, on the information being held in an Archive. This period extends into the indefinite future.
- **Long Term Preservation:** The act of maintaining information, independently understandable by a Designated Community, and with evidence supporting its Authenticity, over the Long Term.

OAIS Functional entities

The roles provided by each of the functional entities in Figure 1 are summarized as follows:

Ingest

The Ingest Functional Entity provides the services and functions to receive Submission Information Packages (SIPs) from Data Producers (or from a repository outsourcing its LTP service to a dedicated archive) and to prepare the contents for storage and management within the Archive. Ingest functions include:

- receiving SIPs
- Performing quality assurance on SIPs

- Generating Archival Information Packages (AIP) which comply with the Archive's data formatting and documentation standards
- Extracting Descriptive Information from the AIPs for inclusion in the Archive metadatabase
- Coordinating updates to Archival Storage and Data Management.

Archival Storage

The Archival Storage Functional Entity provides the services and functions for the storage, maintenance and retrieval of AIPs. Archival Storage functions include:

- Receiving AIPs from Ingest and adding them to permanent storage
- Managing the storage hierarchy
- Refreshing the media on which Archive holdings are stored
- Performing routine and special error checking
- Providing disaster recovery capabilities
- Providing AIPs to Access to fulfill orders.

Data Management

The Data Management Functional Entity provides the services and functions for populating, maintaining, and accessing both Descriptive Information which identifies and documents Archive holdings and administrative data used to manage the Archive. Data Management functions include:

- Administering the Archive database functions (maintaining schema and view definitions, and referential integrity)
- Performing database updates (loading new descriptive information or Archive administrative data)
- Performing queries on the data management data to generate query responses
- Producing reports from these query responses.

Administration

The Administration Functional Entity provides the services and functions for the overall operation of the Archive system. Administration functions include:

- Soliciting and negotiating submission agreements with Producers
- Auditing submissions to ensure that they meet Archive standards
- Maintaining configuration management of system hardware and software.
- Monitoring and improving Archive operations
- Making inventories and reporting on the contents of the Archive
- Migrating/updating the contents of the Archive.
- Establishing and maintaining Archive standards and policies
- Providing customer support
- Activating stored requests.

Preservation Planning

The Preservation Planning Functional Entity provides the services and functions for monitoring the environment of the Archive, providing recommendations and preservation plans to ensure that the information stored in the Archive remains accessible to, and understandable by, the Designated Community over the Long Term, even if the original computing environment becomes obsolete. Preservation Planning functions include:

- Evaluating the contents of the Archive and periodically recommending archival information updates
- Recommending the migration of current Archive holdings
- Developing recommendations for Archive standards and policies
- Providing periodic risk analysis reports
- Monitoring changes in the technology environment
- Monitoring changes in the Designated Community's service requirements and Knowledge Base
- Designing Information Package templates, providing design assistance and review to specialize these templates into SIPs and AIPs for specific submissions
- Developing detailed Migration plans, software prototypes and test plans to enable implementation of Administration migration goals.

Access

The Access Functional Entity provides the services and functions that support Consumers in determining the existence, description, location and availability of information stored in the Archive, and allowing Consumers to request and receive information products. Access functions include:

- Communicating with Consumers to receive requests
- Applying controls to limit access to specially protected information
- Coordinating the execution of requests to successful completion
- Generating responses (Dissemination Information Packages, query responses, reports) and delivering the responses to Consumers.

Common Services

In addition to the functional entities described above, according to the OAIS reference model there are various Common Services (not shown in the diagram) assumed to be available. They constitute the computing environment in which the Archive functions and have a supporting role. Think of the Operating System (providing basic functions such as naming and directory services) and the Computer Network (providing e.g. communication and file transfer functions), but also Security and Backup services are reckoned to be in this category.

Appendix 2. Recurring monitoring processes for LTP

This is an overview of processes in the [LTP Institution] which contribute to Preservation Planning, monitoring community, technology, legal or strategic developments, and risks.

Nr.	Process	Frequency	Responsible
1	<p>Monitor the [LTP Service]'s designated communities for developments that may affect the [LTP Service], such as – requested – changes in technologies or file formats that communities use.</p> <p>This is done in contacts with the communities, e.g. during data acquisition, collaboration projects, membership of European Research Infrastructures, pilot studies with data producers, and training & consultancy, including workshops and conferences.</p> <p>Furthermore, the Business Intelligence Team (BIT) contributes to this monitoring activity, both supply-driven (from BIT to the [LTP Service]) and demand-driven (from the [LTP Service] to BIT).</p>	Daily	[LTP Service] Team Lead + Business Intelligence Team
2	<p>Check and maintain [LTP Institution]'s preferred formats list for obsolescence and completeness (given mission and scope of the [LTP Institution]). If not:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analyse and select alternative preferred formats; • Migrate all relevant files from outdated formats to successor formats, conforming the [LTP Institution] updated preferred formats guidelines; • Update the relevant internal & external documents 	On a regular basis	Preservation Officer + "Preferred Formats" Team
3	<p>Check the potential impact on the [LTP Service]] of – expected – legal and/or regulatory changes, including codes of conduct (e.g. with respect to personal data, database law, etc.)</p>	Continuously	Legal Advisor
4	<p>Monitor [LTP Institution]'s ICT systems and storage facilities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monitor archival system • Monitor storage media • Check backup and recovery procedures 	Continuously	IT Support + external storage provider
5	<p>Monitor potential external threats to the ICT systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodic security updates to all systems • Keep security policy up-to-date 	Continuously, plus periodic updates of the security policy	Security Officer
6	<p>Monitor Preservation Plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is it still up-to-date or is there a reason to update? • Consequences of revisions? 	Biannually	[LTP Service] Team Lead

7	Update the [LTP Institution] multiannual strategy, including the [LTP-service], strategic goals and designated communities	Every four-five years	Director [LTP Institution]
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Appendix 3. Legal and Statutory Context and Requirements

The LTP Policy needs to conform to national and international law, statutory regulations, and business requirements of the [LTP Institution]. **The following legislations**, regulations, codes of conduct and guidelines are relevant for the management and LTP of research data and related digital assets:

European legislation and regulations

- Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (PE/28/2019/REV/1 - in brief Open Data Directive, formerly Public Sector Information (PSI) Directive): <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32019L1024>¹⁸
- Directive 96/9/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 March 1996 on the legal protection of databases (in brief: Database Directive): <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CELEX:31996L0009:EN:HTML>.¹⁹
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (General Data Protection Regulation), repealing Directive 95/46/EC (in brief: GDPR): <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679>. An important GDPR tool in which the responsibilities for data protection are described is the Data Processing Agreement: <https://gdpr.eu/data-processing-agreement/>

International codes of conduct

- Singapore Statement on Research Integrity (2010): <http://wcrif.org/guidance/singapore-statement>
- OECD Best Practices for Ensuring Scientific Integrity and Preventing Misconduct (2007): <https://www.oecd.org/science/inno/40188303.pdf>
- ALLEA European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2017): <http://www.allea.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf>

¹⁸ The Open Data Directive will be complemented by the Data Governance Act (DGA), the legislative framework to facilitate data-sharing (COM/2020/767 final, officially proposed by the EC on 25 November 2020. See:

<https://data.europa.eu/en/highlights/data-governance-act-open-data-directive> for background and

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32019L1024>) for the draft text..

¹⁹ The directive is being reviewed as part of a proposed Data Act, see:

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_Act_\(European_Union\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_Act_(European_Union)).

- UNESCO Recommendation on Science and Scientific Researchers (2017):
http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=49455&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- Guidelines of the Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE):
<https://publicationethics.org/resources/guidelines>

Data archiving guidelines

- The ten LTP Principles (listed above in section 2.2):
<https://www.crl.edu/archiving-preservation/digital-archives/metrics-assessing-and-certifying/core-re>
- The FAIR Data Principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- The mandatory responsibilities of an Open Archival Information System (OAIS):
<http://www.oais.info/>
- The requirements of
 - the CoreTrustSeal: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>
 - and/or optionally nestorSeal DIN 31644: <https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de>
 - and/or ISO 16363 <https://www.iso.org/standard/56510.html>

National legislation and codes of conduct (example for The Netherlands)

- Uitvoeringswet Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (UAVG); the Dutch law implementing the European GDPR (16 May 2018, valid from 1 July 2021).
<https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0040940/2021-07-01>
- Databankenwet (1999), the Dutch Database Act, implementing the European Database Directive: <https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0010591/2021-06-07>
- Auteurswet; Dutch Copyright Act (1912/latest update 7/6/2021):
<https://wetten.overheid.nl/BWBR0001886/2021-06-07>
- The Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity 2018 (<https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-2cj-nwwu>), replacing the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Academic Practice (2014 revision).²⁰

²⁰ The 2014 revision of the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Scientific Practice prescribed a minimum retention period of ten years for raw research data (article 3.3.) The new Code of Conduct for Research Integrity 2018 no longer specifies a minimum retention period, but says that data, software codes, protocols, research material and corresponding metadata should be stored *permanently* (as far as possible; section 4.4., art. 12).

Appendix 4. Selected terms and abbreviations used

In the context of digital preservation, the terms principles, strategy, policy and plan(ning) are often used, sometimes interchangeably. However, it makes sense to make distinction between the terms:

- A *principle* is a basic proposition that serves as the foundation for a system of belief or behaviour or for a chain of reasoning. In this context, LTP principles are fundamental premises concerning the archiving of digital materials.
- A *policy* is defined as the set of guidelines, rules and procedures developed by an organisation to govern its actions (often in recurring situations). They define the limits (do's and don'ts) within which decisions must be made, and are to be widely communicated and available and accessible, both to the organisation's staff and its customers.
- A *strategy* is a high-level plan of action designed to achieve one or more of the organisation's objectives. A strategy fills the gap between "where we are" and "where we want to be", that is, "how are we going to get there?" It relates to how an organisation allocates and uses materials and human resources.
- A *plan* explains in more detail how a strategy will be executed; it is the operational side of the strategy.²¹

The focus of the task at hand here is the formulation of a model LTP Policy Template, i.e. a set of guidelines, rules and procedures, but it will be useful to base this policy on generally acceptable principles. In addition to these terms, also the term combination "**policy framework**" occurs. This is a somewhat vague term, as all of the terms mentioned after the bullets above can be part of such a "framework", and many more things as well²².

A second terminological clarification concerns the distinction between digital preservation and long-term preservation (LTP), two terms that are also often used indiscriminately. In *digital preservation* *sec*, there is no assumption whatsoever about the time span, although in practice, it often assumes the long term. Although the term *LTP* does not explicitly state it is about digital objects, this is obvious in this context. The term itself does not give a specification about the length of "long term", which can be either indefinite or definite, and is usually longer than 5 or 10 years²³. It is clear that the policies we are about to formulate concern the long term. To be exact, we are talking here about a *long-term digital preservation* policy.

For practical reasons, moreover, it is sometimes necessary to draw distinction between the *institution* providing a LTP service (or LTP Institution or LTP Service Provider) and the *LTP service* itself. To clarify the point in an example: DANS, an Institute of the Royal Netherlands

²¹ Note that according to the OAIS reference model, the "preservation planning function" has a more limited definition (see Appendix 1).

²² The Digital Preservation Policy Framework by Ohio State University Libraries (OSUL) provides an idea of the diversity of subjects to be covered by such a framework, see: https://library.osu.edu/documents/SDIWG/Digital_Preservation_Policy_Framework.pdf

²³ Jeff Rothenberg is often quoted for his expression: "digital information lasts forever—or five years, whichever comes first" in "Ensuring the Longevity of Digital Information", RAND Corporation, 22/01/1999, p. 2. <https://www.clir.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/6/ensuring.pdf>

Academy of Arts and Science (KNAW) is a LTP Service Provider; it provides several services, among which a LTP Service, which is called the “Data Vault”. For a LTP Service, one or more systems or components of systems may be used.

List of Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AUP	Acceptable Use Policy
BIT	Business Intelligence Team (of DANS)
CSC	IT Center for Science Ltd. (Tieteen Tietotekniikan Keskus Oy)
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DDPS	DICE Digital Preservation Service
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DPC	Digital Preservation Coalition
DPS	Data Privacy Statement
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC TF LT	EOSC - Task Force - Long Term Data Preservation
EU	European Union
EUDAT	European Data Infrastructure
EUDAT CDI	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KNAW	Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen (Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences)
LTP	Long-term preservation
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
PID	Persistent Identifier
SDA	Service Distribution Agreement
SLA	Service Level Agreement

SMF	Service Management Framework (of EUDAT)
SURF	Samenwerkende Universitaire Reken Faciliteiten
UAVG	Uitvoeringswet Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (UAVG); the Dutch law implementing the European GDPR

Part IV: Specifics for EUDAT

Appendix 5. Applying the Long-Term Preservation Policy Template

EUDAT B2SHARE as a designated community or communities

B2SHARE is described as an EUDAT service for “*researchers, scientific communities and citizen scientists*” to store and share *small-scale research data* (including *software code*) from *diverse contexts*. B2SHARE is a self-depository system. Researchers (data producers) are responsible for successfully uploading data and for providing documentation. The digital objects stored in EUDAT B2SHARE can be distinguished on three levels:

- Community: a collection of datasets, created by and relevant for a certain group of researchers.
- Record: an organized collection of data files belonging to a research project, or created by one researcher or research group, together with their descriptions (metadata).
- File: a digital file in which data is stored; it typically has a particular organisation or format, which is usually reflected by a file naming convention (such as the file extension). A Record or Dataset usually contains one or more (data) files, although Records/Datasets may only contain metadata without data files (e.g. as “tombstones” or references to data stored elsewhere).

Only registered users of B2SHARE can create new records and upload data into these records. The current default maximum size for a record is 20 GB and for an individual file 10 GB. The uploading of large numbers of files or the creation of large numbers of records is not considered “[fair use](#)” by the B2SHARE service. If researchers want to publish many datasets, they should contact EUDAT through their [service request portal](#).

This description makes clear that the service is intended for a varied audience:

- For individual researchers as well as scientific communities.
- For professional and citizen scientists.
- For research data and software of small to moderate size.
- “From diverse contexts”, which we interpret as from various disciplines.

Like many other discipline-independent and institutional repositories, B2SHARE was set up for a broad range of scientific and scholarly uses. The characteristics and needs of a diversity of scientific communities were incorporated in the design and functionality of the service.

If long-term preservation is outsourced to a dedicated archive, its [LTP Service] inherits the researchers and communities served by B2SHARE as users by proxy. Still, this LTP Policy was originally formulated to satisfy the demands of EUDAT B2SHARE, which we may also consider as a designated community here.

Applying the LTP Policy Template for B2SHARE and B2SAFE

On the EUDAT website, B2SAFE is described as “a robust and highly available service which allows community and departmental repositories to implement data management policies on their research data across multiple administrative domains in a trustworthy manner. It offers an abstraction layer of large scale, heterogeneous data storages, guards against data loss in

long-term archiving, allows to optimize access for users (e.g. from different regions), brings data closer to facilities for compute-intensive analysis²⁴.

To understand how the LTP Policy applies to a service we need to understand the commonalities and differences of the B2SHARE and B2SAFE services and technologies. Both services have been onboarded on the EOSC Service Catalogue²⁵ and are offered free-at-the-point-of-use via virtual access through the DICE project.

Table 3 describes the B2SHARE and B2SAFE services and capabilities related to aspects of long-term preservation.

Table 3. Service description of B2SHARE and B2SAFE

	B2SHARE	B2SAFE
EOSC Service Catalogue	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/b2share	https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/b2safe
Short description	B2SHARE is a user-friendly, reliable and trustworthy way for researchers, scientific communities and citizen scientists to store, publish and share research data in a FAIR way. B2SHARE is a solution that facilitates research data storage, guarantees long-term persistence of data and allows data, results or ideas to be shared worldwide. B2SHARE supports community domains with metadata extensions, access rules and publishing workflows. EUDAT offers communities and organisations customised instances and/or access to repositories supporting large datasets.	B2SAFE is a robust and highly available service which allows community and departmental repositories to implement data management policies on their research data across multiple administrative domains in a trustworthy manner. It offers an abstraction layer of large scale, heterogeneous data storages, guards against data loss in long-term archiving, allows to optimize access for users (e.g. from different regions) and brings data closer to facilities for compute-intensive analysis.
Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support of metadata descriptions via the EUDAT Core metadata schema • Registers DOIs for datasets and Handle PIDs for data objects • Supports versioning • Harvested by B2FIND and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for data management policies (e.g. registration of PIDs, cross-site replication, data integrity checks) • Support for policies customised to community and organisational needs

²⁴ "What is B2SAFE?" on <https://www.eudat.eu/catalogue/b2safe> (visited 18/11/2022).

²⁵ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/> (visited 18/11/2022).

	B2SHARE	B2SAFE
	<p>OpenAIRE Explore</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct upload from B2DROP • Accessible via a Web GUI and a REST API to support automatic publishing workflows • Supports community domains • Allows communities to define metadata extensions, access rules and publishing workflows • Allows references to externally hosted data objects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for less frequently used archival data, but can also support active data • Support for large scale storage resources (e.g up to PB-scale) • A single namespace across heterogeneous storages • Supports integration with different kind of storage systems (e.g. tape-based HSM, POSIX filesystems, object storage) • Access via GridFTP, WebDAV, iRODS commands • Service offered by a network of EUDAT service providers
Curation level	Enhanced	Bit preservation
Designated community	Yes, at time of writing 22 community domains are supported	Yes, is in agreement with the customer and contract
Access	Public free-to-use service, depositors need to register an account	Closed service, customers need to request access
Metadata	Yes, supports metadata via EUDAT metadata schema and community specific extensions	Optionally, basic object information is maintained, user descriptive metadata can be provided
PID	Yes, registers DOIs for the landing pages of datasets and Handle PIDs for individual data objects	Yes, PIDs for data objects are automatically registered via the PID data management policy
License	Optionally, licenses can be added to a dataset	No, users are not able to specify a license
Versioning	Yes, versioning is supported	No, options available to implement a versioning policy
Deletion of datasets	Yes, only authorised staff are able to delete published data records	No, data owners are allowed to delete data objects

As can be seen in Table 2, the B2SHARE and B2SAFE services have different aims with respect to curation levels. B2SHARE aims at an enhanced curation level, while the aim of B2SAFE is bit preservation, therefore the B2SHARE and B2SAFE services support different capabilities.

From the LTP Policy comparison made in Table 4, Appendix 7 it can be concluded that the B2SHARE CDI and the B2SAFE services comply to a large extent with the LTP criteria as defined in Table 1 for the aimed curation levels.

Appendix 6. Available Licenses for digital assets uploaded to the EUDAT B2SHARE service

All licenses are open licences. However, some of these licenses require compliance with conditions such as giving appropriate credit via citation, providing a link to the license, indicating if changes were made, or non-commercial use. In cases where these conditions apply, creating an account and logging into the [LTP Service] is necessary in order to guarantee compliance²⁶.

License name	URL
Affero General Public License 3 (AGPL-3.0)	http://opensource.org/licenses/AGPL-3.0
Apache License 2	http://www.apache.org/licenses/LICENSE-2.0
Artistic License 1.0	http://opensource.org/licenses/Artistic-Perl-1.0
Artistic License 2.0	http://opensource.org/licenses/Artistic-2.0
Common Development and Distribution License (CDDL-1.0)	http://opensource.org/licenses/CDDL-1.0
Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY)	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivs (CC-BY-ND)	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nd/4.0/
Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial (CC-BY-NC)	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/
Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs (CC-BY-NC-ND)	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/
Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC-BY-NC-SA)	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/
Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike (CC-BY-SA)	http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/

²⁶ See: <https://github.com/ufal/public-license-selector/#available-licenses> (last visited 18/11/2022).

Eclipse Public License 1.0 (EPL-1.0)	http://opensource.org/licenses/EPL-1.0
GNU General Public License 2 or later (GPL-2.0)	http://opensource.org/licenses/GPL-2.0
GNU General Public License 3 (GPL-3.0)	http://opensource.org/licenses/GPL-3.0
GNU Library or "Lesser" General Public License 2.1 or later (LGPL-2.1)	http://opensource.org/licenses/LGPL-2.1
GNU Library or "Lesser" General Public License 3.0 (LGPL-3.0)	http://opensource.org/licenses/LGPL-3.0
Mozilla Public License 2.0	http://opensource.org/licenses/MPL-2.0
Public Domain Dedication (CC Zero)	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/
Public Domain Mark (PD)	http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/
The BSD 2-Clause "Simplified" or "FreeBSD" License	http://opensource.org/licenses/BSD-2-Clause
The BSD 3-Clause "New" or "Revised" License (BSD)	http://opensource.org/licenses/BSD-3-Clause
The MIT License (MIT)	http://opensource.org/licenses/mit-license.php

Appendix 7. LTP compliance comparison between B2SHARE and B2SAFE

In Table 4 on the next pages an assessment and comparison is made between B2SHARE and B2SAFE on compliance to the articles in the Long Term Preservation Policy template. The table lists an overview of all the sections and articles provided by the LTP Policy Template and the curation status in both services.

Codes in Column "Curation":

- S = Needs to be Specified
- X = Mandatory for this Curation level (see table 1)
- enhanced = Multiple checks as specified in section 2.5.2 of the LTP are applied
- extended = Multiple options as specified in sections 2.5.3, 3.1, 3.4 of the LTP are applied
- N/A = Not Applicable

Codes in Column "Status":

- Yes = The service supports the LTP Policy article.
- No = The service does not support the LTP Policy article.
- Partially = The service partially complies with LTP Policy article, a short explanation is provided.
- Optional = The service provides capabilities to comply with the LTP Policy article but are optional, and/or not mandatory for the user and/or designated community to be applied, a short explanation is provided.
- N/A = Not Applicable

Table 4. LTP Policy comparison between B2SHARE and B2SAFE

Section and Article	Brief description	Data service					
		B2SHARE			B2SAFE		
		https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/b2share			https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/b2safe		
		Curation: Enhanced	Status	Explanation	Curation: Bit preservation	Status	Explanation
I. Objectives, scope and delimitation of this policy							
1.1	General aim of LTP Policy	S		B2SHARE is a user-friendly, reliable and trustworthy way for researchers, scientific communities and citizen scientists to store, publish and share research data in a FAIR way.	S		B2SAFE is a robust and highly available service which allows community and departmental repositories to implement data management policies on their research data across multiple administrative domains in a trustworthy manner.
1.2	Specific aims	S		B2SHARE is a solution that facilitates research data storage, guarantees long-term persistence of data and allows data, results or ideas to be shared worldwide.	S		B2SAFE offers an abstraction layer of large scale, heterogeneous data storages, guards against data loss in long-term archiving, and allows optimized access for users (e.g. from different regions),
1.3	Scope of LTP Policy	S		The policy, when applied, is only applicable to the B2SHARE central service (https://b2share.eudat.eu/)	S		When included in a binding contract, the policy is only applicable to the B2SAFE instances involved within the contract.
1.4	Responsibility	S		EUDAT Ltd is the service organisation responsible for the B2SHARE service. CSC is the service provider partner	S		Service is not a public service and is only offered on the basis of a contract including a SLA and DPA. EUDAT contracts are underpinned by a Service

				hosting and operating the service on behalf of EUDAT.			Distribution Agreement (SDA) and OLA with the service providers hosting and operating the service instances.
1.5	Remit and mission	S		EUDAT's vision is Data is shared and preserved across borders and disciplines. Achieving this vision means enabling data stewardship within and between European research communities through a Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI), a common model and service infrastructure for managing data spanning all European research data centres and community data repositories.	S		EUDAT's vision is Data is shared and preserved across borders and disciplines. Achieving this vision means enabling data stewardship within and between European research communities through a Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI), a common model and service infrastructure for managing data spanning all European research data centres and community data repositories.
1.6	Preservation duration	S	Partially	The EUDAT CDI partnership agreement guarantees service provision of the EUDAT services for a period of 10 years by its members.	S	Yes	Is in agreement with the customer and contract.
1.7	Designated community	S	Yes	On request of research communities community domains have been defined to support deposits of data records on basis community-defined metadata templates.	S	Yes	Is in agreement with the customer and contract.
2. Ingest							
2.1	Submission Information Package for Ingest	X	Yes	Supports metadata and data objects.	X	Optional	Users are able to store AIP packages accompanying the data objects, but this is not mandatory.
2.2	Metadata index and Cataloguing	X	Optional	Support 2 publication workflows: - Open publication workflow in which users are allowed to directly publish data records	N/A	No	N/A within the specified curation level

				- Reviewed publication workflow in which users are only allowed to submit draft data records which are reviewed before publication			
2.3	Licenses	X	Optional	Specifying a license is an optional field	N/A	No	
2.4	Persistent Identifiers	X	Yes	Assigns a DOI and Handle PID to the landing page of the data records and Handle PIDs to each of the ingested data objects	N/A	Yes	Assigns Handle PIDs to each of the ingested data objects
	Additional PIDs	N/A	Yes	For each creator the following Identifiers can be optionally specified: - Affiliation (e.g. RoR) - Name identifier (e.g. ORCID)	N/A	No	N/A within the specified curation level
2.5	Quality control	enhanced checks of metadata	Partially	See sub-requirements below.	none	No	
2.5.1	Metadata supplied by depositor	X	Yes	Metadata needs to be specified according to community defined metadata templates.	N/A	No	
2.5.2	Ingest control	enhanced	Partially	Checksums are automatically generated during deposit, depositors are required to describe data with minimum metadata, including creators and contact personal data. No preferred data formats are specified and therefore no re-formatting is required.	none	Partially	Checksums are automatically calculated and verified.
2.5.3	Required metadata fields	extended	Yes	Depositors need to specify Title, 1 or more Creators, description, if data is open access or not, metadata is always open, an embargo period and a publication date can be specified.	none	No	N/A within the specified curation level

				Different community domains are defined, including community defined metadata extensions.				
2.5.4	Responsibility for metadata	X	Yes	Independent from the publication workflow, the depositor needs to provide the minimum required mandatory fields.	N/A	No		
2.5.5	Notification of deficient metadata	X	Optional	Is supported via the reviewed publication workflow and can be configured per designated community.	N/A	No		
2.5.6	Data and metadata corrections	X	Yes	Major changes are supported via the versioning feature, minor changes are supported via the reviewed publication workflow and/or can be made by the depositor.	N/A	No		
When LTP is outsourced								
2.6	Submission Information Package for Ingest	X	N/A	At time of writing LTP is not outsourced	M	N/A	At time of writing LTP is not outsourced	
2.7	Metadata index and Cataloguing	X	N/A		N/A	N/A		
2.8	Licenses	X	N/A		N/A	N/A		
2.9	Persistent Identifiers	X	N/A		N/A	N/A		
2.10	Additional PIDs	X	N/A		N/A	N/A		
2.11	Quality control	basic checks of metadata	N/A		N/A	N/A		
2.11.1	Metadata supplied by depositor	X	N/A		N/A	N/A		
2.11.2	Ingest control	basic	N/A		N/A	N/A		

2.11.3	Mapping of metadata	X	N/A		N/A	N/A	
2.11.4	Required metadata fields	basic	N/A		N/A	N/A	
2.11.5	Responsibility for metadata	X	N/A		N/A	N/A	
2.11.6	Notification of deficient metadata	X	N/A		N/A	N/A	
2.11.7	Data and metadata corrections	X	N/A		N/A	N/A	
3. Archival Storage							
3.1	Archival actions and chain of provenance	extended	Partially	Via version management changes to licenses, metadata and file format versions are documented.	none	No	N/A within the specified curation level
3.2	Archival storage of AIPs	X	Yes	For all data records in which all data is locally maintained, AIP information is stored within the storage facilities. Data objects which are externally hosted only PID references are maintained.	X	Yes	For each data object uploaded a checksum is calculated and a PID maintained.
3.3	No responsibility for data stored externally	X	Yes	Service provider does not assume responsibility for externally hosted data objects.	S	Yes	Via the replication policy data objects can be replicated across multiple locations, for each of the locations checksums are calculated and verified and PIDs are maintained and linked to each other.
3.4	Integrity and security measures	extended	Partially	Within the EUDAT CDI infrastructure, EUDAT Ltd has OLA agreements with the service providers running services on behalf of EUDAT, responsibility to perform security audits is delegated to the service providers running the services. Security incidents, including data loss, are managed through the EUDAT CSIRT (Computer Security	check sums	Yes	Within the EUDAT CDI infrastructure, EUDAT Ltd has OLA agreements with the service providers running services on behalf of EUDAT, responsibility to perform security audits is delegated to the service providers running the services. Security incidents, including data loss, are managed through the EUDAT CSIRT (Computer Security

				Incident Response Team). Data alteration and/or corruption is considered as data loss.			Incident Response Team). Data alteration and/or corruption is considered as data loss. During the upload of the data, checksums are automatically calculated and verified.
3.5	Outsourcing storage to external provider	S	Yes	EUDAT Ltd has OLA agreements with the service providers running services on behalf of EUDAT. The OLA agreement has service level targets on the availability and quality of the service, service provisioning, incident handling, support and backups. The services are provided according to FitSM processes.	S	Yes	EUDAT Ltd has OLA agreements with the service providers running services on behalf of EUDAT. The OLA agreement has service level targets on the availability and quality of the service, service provisioning, incident handling, support and backups. The services are provided according to FitSM processes. Via the replication policy multiple copies across different locations can be created.
4. Data Management							
4.1	Metadata catalogue maintenance	X	Yes	A database is maintained with metadata which is searchable. The B2SHARE technology supports community metadata schemas on the basis of the EUDAT Core metadata schema with optional community extensions.	N/A	Partially	A database is maintained with basic data object information (file name, user, groups, permissions). In the format of triples also user specified metadata can be provided which is searchable via command line tools. Users are not required to specify user descriptive metadata.
4.2	Archival metadata supporting version control	X	Yes	Service supports versioning via which change control is being managed	X	No	Versioning is not supported
4.3.1	Derived and dissemination formats	X	Yes	Data objects are maintained as-is, no derived formats are created	N/A	No	N/A within the specified curation level
4.3.2	Authenticity and integrity of AIPs	X	Yes	A user can only remove draft data records, published data records cannot be removed, only by the authorised staff. Published data	X	Yes	During the upload of the data, checksums are automatically calculated and verified.

				records can only be updated via versioning. For each of the data objects checksums are generated and maintained to verify the integrity of the data objects.			
4.3.3	Documentation of chain of custody	X	Yes	Service supports versioning via which change control is being managed	N/A	No	N/A within the specified curation level
4.4	Preferred and accepted file formats	X	No	Users are free to upload data in any data format and are maintained as-is	N/A	No	
4.5	Obsolescence of file formats	N/A	No		N/A	No	
4.6.1	Migration of preferred formats	N/A	No		N/A	No	
4.6.2	Preserving outdated formats	N/A	No		N/A	No	
4.7	Deletion of datasets and files	X	Yes	Only authorised staff are able to delete published data records	X	No	Data owners are allowed to delete data objects
4.8	Tombstone records for deleted datasets	X	No	No tombstone records are created	X	No	No tombstone records are created
5. Administration							
5.1	Monitoring operations and reporting	S	Yes	The availability and reliability of the B2SHARE CDI service are actively monitored in the EUDAT central monitoring service.	S	Yes	The availability and reliability of B2SAFE instances are actively monitored in the EUDAT central monitoring service.
5.2	LTP Strategy and upgrading the [LTP Service]	S	Yes	A roadmap of the service and technology is maintained	S	Yes	A roadmap of the service and technology is maintained
5.3	Planning and control cycle	S	Yes		S	Yes	
5.4	Strategic and operational evaluations	S	Yes	EUDAT is a member organisation, the strategic functioning and direction is monitored by the EUDAT Council.	S	Yes	EUDAT is a member organisation, the strategic functioning and direction is monitored by the EUDAT Council.

5.5	Advisory board	S	Yes	EUDAT has a User Board with representatives from the scientific communities.	S	Yes	EUDAT has a User Board with representatives from the scientific communities.
5.6	Customer support	S	Yes	Customer and user support is provided via the EUDAT Helpdesk	S	Yes	Customer and user support is provided via the EUDAT Helpdesk
5.7	Legal and statutory regulations	S	Partially	Terms of Use, Acceptable use Policy and Data Privacy Statement are available.	S	Partially	Service is not a public service and is only offered on the basis of a contract including a SLA and DPA. EUDAT contracts are underpinned by a SDA and OLA with the service providers hosting and operating the service instances.
6. Preservation Planning							
6.1	Monitoring the content of the [LTP Service]	X	Yes	Periodically metrics are published on usage of the service.	X	No	Data records are maintained as-is
6.2	Reviewing and updating list of preferred formats	X	No	No preferred file format list is maintained	N/A	No	N/A within the specified curation level
6.3	Other monitoring for preservation planning	X			N/A		
6.3.1	Security risks	X	Yes	Security risks are regular and continuously monitored via the ISM (Information Security Management process and procedures.	N/A	Yes	Security risks are regular and continuously monitored via the ISM (Information Security Management process and procedures.
6.3.2	Technology watch	X	Yes	Technology watch is a continuous aspect within the service development process	N/A	Yes	Technology watch is a continuous aspect within the service development process
6.3.3	Service requirements	X	Yes	Via the issues in the software repository a feature request list is maintained	N/A	Yes	Via the issues in the software repository a feature request list is maintained

6.4	Roles and responsibilities, confidentiality, liability	X	Yes	The EUDAT secretariat will be responsible for maintaining the LTP Policy, the implementation of the policy is delegated to the service provider running an instance of the service on behalf of EUDAT on the basis of the OLA agreement.	N/A	Yes	The EUDAT secretariat is responsible for maintaining the LTP Policy, the implementation of the policy is delegated to the service provider running an instance of the service on behalf of EUDAT on the basis of an OLA agreement.
6.5.1	Funding adequate for sustaining [LTP Service]	X	Partially	The EUDAT CDI partnership agreement guarantees service provision of the EUDAT services for a period of 10 years by its members.	N/A	Partially	The EUDAT CDI partnership agreement guarantees service provision of the EUDAT services for a period of 10 years by its members.
6.5.2	Contingency plan	X	Yes	Yes, for the duration of the EUDAT CDI Partnership agreement. CSC is the service provider partner hosting and operating the service on behalf of the EUDAT. CSC is a level 1 partner of the EUDAT CDI.	N/A	Yes	Yes, for the duration of the EUDAT CDI Partnership agreement. If a more comprehensive contingency plan is required, this can be part of a contract.
7. Access							
7.1	Access functions (user interface, API)	S	Yes	A WUI and APIs are provided to access the service, including an OAI-PMH endpoint for harvesting.	S	Partially	Service is not accessible via a WUI, different APIs are provided to up/download and manage data.
7.2	Metadata openly accessible	S	Yes	Metadata is open accessible, data can be closed	S	No	Default data is only accessible to the owner.
7.3	User registration for accessing licensed datasets	S	No	Default data is open accessible. Users uploading a data record can close access to the data objects. If this is the case, users interested to download the data objects must request access.	S	optional	Optionally the owner can share data with registered users.
7.4	CC Waiver and Open Access without registration	S	Yes	Users do not need to register an account or to login to access Open Access data records and objects.	S	No	Default data is only accessible to the owner.

7.5	Conditions of use and citation recommendation	S	No	No explicit statements and/or citation recommendations are made.	S	No	No explicit statements and/or citation recommendations are made.
When LTP is outsourced							
7.6	Access through original data service via PID	S	No	At time of writing LTP is not outsourced	S	Yes	When data is replicated, PIDs to all copies of the data are interreferenced
7.7	Access in case original data service discontinued	S	No		S	optional	When data is replicated across multiple locations, access to the replicated copies can be provided.

Appendix 8. Agreement structure within EUDAT

The EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure (or EUDAT CDI) is one of the largest infrastructures of integrated data services and resources supporting research in Europe. It is sustained by a network of more than 20 European research organisations, data and computing centres that in September 2016 have signed a partnership agreement to maintain the EUDAT CDI for the next 10 years and in 2018 have supported the establishment of the limited liability company, EUDAT Ltd.

The EUDAT CDI partnership agreement includes a Service Management Framework (SMF) which defines the principles, policies, agreement framework and structured processes governing the EUDAT collaborative data infrastructure (CDI). This structure is schematically shown in Figure 2.

The purpose of the SMF is to clarify the operational constituents, roles and responsibilities of the *Service Provider* and to ensure a high quality of the service delivery to the *Customers* and their users.

Figure 2. Current EUDAT agreement structure

The agreement structure within EUDAT consists of agreements between a customer and EUDAT Ltd which are supported by agreements between EUDAT Ltd and the members who are hosting and operating the services and resources provided through EUDAT Ltd.

- Customer: The customer is the organization and/or mandated person with whom EUDAT Ltd has a binding contract for the delivery of the services and resources. The customer is also the entity that deposits data in the EUDAT service. The contract is underpinned by a Service Level Agreement (SLA) describing the service level targets

and responsibilities between EUDAT Ltd and customers. Within the EUDAT CDI infrastructure and services at different levels personal data is being managed. To ensure that this personal data is managed according to the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR) the Data Processing Agreement (DPA) is used.

- *Service provider:* To underpin the customer contracts EUDAT Ltd has agreements with level 1 CDI members in provisioning of services and resources through EUDAT. To allow the marketing and reselling of services to customers, EUDAT Ltd has Service Delivery Agreements with the service providers offering services through EUDAT. Underpinning the SLA's with customers, but also the provisioning of EUDAT central services (e.g. B2SHARE) and the operational tools, EUDAT Ltd has Operational Level Agreements.
- *User:* The user is the actual user of the service, who has an account to make use of the service. Access and usage of the service is underpinned by an Acceptable Use Policy (AUP) and Data Privacy Statement (DPS) . The AUP sets out the terms under which you may access our Services and applies as soon as you access and/or use. The DPS describes what personal data and how this is being handled within EUDAT services. Therefore the DPS are service specific.

The scope of the Long Term Preservation task within DICE is to extend the EUDAT agreement framework with a Long Term Preservation policy and agreement supporting the service delivery of the B2SHARE and B2SAFE services through EUDAT Ltd.

- **Long Term Preservation Policy (LTP Policy)** describes preservation policy to ensure the long-term preservation and accessibility of electronic information while ensuring the highest level of authenticity possible.
- **Long Term Preservation Agreement (LTP Agreement)** supplements the SLA and OLA agreements describing the preservation level, on the basis of the LTP Policy, agreed either between the customer and EUDAT Ltd and/or between EUDAT Ltd and the organisation providing the LTP service.

Depending on the capabilities and aim of the service and service provider, a service provider can decide to support the full LTP Policy by itself, or decide to make use of an external service provider to outsource long-term preservation of the data. To be able to do so needs to be organised in the customer contracts, unless this is possible on another legal basis (for instance: the data is in the public domain).

Independent if a service provider delegates the responsibility for the long-term preservation to an external service provider, the service in which the data is initially deposited needs to comply with LTP Policy. When a service provider makes use of an external LTP service and service provider the LTP Policy defines additional requirements the external LTP service provider has to comply with too.

In the following diagrams the EUDAT agreement structure, including the LTP Policy and agreement, is explained. Figure 3 shows a preservation setup in which the service provider takes full responsibility for the LTP Policy. In the context of the EUDAT B2SHARE CDI service, the service is offered as public service by EUDAT and the service is hosted and operated by CSC. Therefore EUDAT is responsible to comply with the LTP Policy, to supply the enhanced curation level towards the users, while CSC is responsible for the execution of the LTP.

Figure 3. Data Repository Service is LTP Service

Figure 4 shows long-term preservation that has been set up with an external LTP service provider. In this example EUDAT has a LTP agreement with a [LTP Institution] (in this case: DANS) for the long-term preservation of data records. Data records are deposited in B2SHARE and are preserved in the Data Vault of DANS.

Figure 4. Long-term preservation is delegated by Data Repository Service to external LTP Service